

A Note on the Use of Adsorption Indicators in Acidimetry and Alkalimetry.

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So far, no investigation appears to have been made in order to find out the applicability of adsorption indicators in acidimetry and alkalimetry. In the present paper attempts have been made to describe a process in which adsorption indicators may be utilised in acidimetry and alkalimetry.

A known volume of standard nitric acid (not less than $N/20$) was taken in a conical flask and a few drops of fluorescein (0.50% soln. of sodium fluoresceinate) and 1 c. c. of 0.5% lead nitrate (approx. $N/30$) solution was added to it and the mixture titrated with caustic soda; the presence of small amounts of sodium carbonate was found to have no effect on the accuracy of the colour reaction. At a certain point the dull-green colour of the solution changes to a brilliant fluorescent green. The addition of alkali was continued in drops. The end-point was ascertained by the sudden disappearance of the fluorescent green colour and consequent development of a distinct yellow colour. The solution becomes turbid at the same time. The solution should be well shaken after the addition of each drop. It is always advisable to add a drop more to ensure the colour change. The colour change is sufficiently delicate to be distinguished even with $N/40$ solutions.

Eosin may be used instead of fluorescein, in which case the colour changes from red fluorescence to a brilliant turbid pink.

The strengths of alkali and acid (nitric acid) determined in this way were compared with those obtained by titration with methyl orange as indicator and the two results were found to be concordant. Hydrochloric and sulphuric acids cannot be estimated in this way as lead chloride and lead sulphate are precipitated.

Acetic acid also may be determined by this way. In this case the fluorescent colour appears much earlier than in the case of nitric acid. This is due to the hydrolysis of sodium acetate formed. But the colour change to yellow is not affected by it, unless the solutions are

concentrated. For the colour reaction depends on the minimum p_n value, at which lead hydroxide may be formed and not on the p_n value of the solution, at which fluorescein assumes its alkaline colour.

The mechanism of the reaction is explained in the following way:—

As soon as the acid is neutralised, the extra drop of alkali reacts with lead nitrate forming lead hydroxide, on which are adsorbed lead and fluorescein ions giving rise to the characteristic red coloured dye-precipitate complex observed by Wellings (*Analyst*, 1933, 58, 331).

The best results are obtained with $N/10$ to $N/15$ solutions. Large excesses of neutral salts affect the colour change to a considerable degree.

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